

Relationship of customers' satisfaction and loyalty on Shariah-compliant hotel in Shah Alam Malaysia

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ABSTRACT

Along with the development of a business hotel in Malaysia, which makes it an effort to improve customer satisfaction factor. Malaysia is the one of Target Islamic Tourism with total number of visitors are from various countries such as Indonesia, Brunei, Kazakhstan, Bangladesh, Arab and other Middle Eastern countries. Moreover, it will lead to a new innovation in the hospitality industry in the concept of Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH). Malaysia is the one of the largest Muslim population that has a good opportunity for developing new innovative market of Islamic hotel. Shah Alam has two hotels that were implementing Shariah-Compliant Hotel concept (SCH) such as Grand Bluewave hotel & Depalma Ampang hotel. Therefore, this research was used simple random sampling method with a total sample of 207 respondents to be answered 52 statements or questions in the form of surveys. Through this study, we will emphasize on factors that support customer satisfaction such as facilities, restaurants, grooming staff and building design. Overall, all variables, received a better response from respondents, more than four (4, Agree). Therefore, these four variables are crucial to the satisfaction of customers who will maintain service quality that can affect to *customer loyalty*

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INTRODUCTION

Islamic Tourism is the one new concept that were attracted for Muslim visitors. Halal food one of the priority during their travel to enjoy with Logo Halal are appear in the restaurant itself. In the tourism industry, (Noorul Huda Mohd Razali, Anuar Talib. 2013) On 11 September 2000, the total number of tourists coming to Malaysia from the Middle East, UK and US was dropped dramatically according to records (Henderson 2017) which was stated by (Battour, M., M.N. Ismail and M. Battor, 2018). Since 11 September 2000, Islamic countries are the main destination chosen by tourists to go to improve the Service Quality that has implemented by the SCH, and for giving explanation that Islamic hotel are not totally different with conventional hotel. Is it new concept that will provide facilities and basic information for Muslim to do prayer obligations. SCH is a good phenomenon has reflected in the Islamic countries of the Middle East which will be implemented in Malaysia. Where *Shariah-Compliant Hotel* is an alternative choice for guest stay as a new attraction.

As Muslim tourists are required to worship wherever they are because it is the demand of our beliefs which includes the pillars of Islam and the pillars of faith as a guide for Muslims every day (Sahida 2011). Where a traveler who is on the trip will certainly be near the name of the hotel, of course, the service from the hotel provides amenities without requested, because visitors cannot leave their religious routine even on the traveling. SCH must give the Qibla direction in the room without having to ask the reception where the Qibla direction is. Because this is the basic of the Shariah-Compliant hotel that must be in the hotel. According to records (Rosenberg, 2009), the Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH) is an analysis for Muslims who are very important and a good object of marketing. Based on quotations from (Islamic Tourism Center, 2015; El-Gohary, 2015) Shariah-Compliant hotels (SCH) can be enjoyed by both Muslims and non-Muslims because the main target is to attract tourists from Muslim countries but not refuse to accept guests who non-Islam. Based on records (Mastercard & CrescentRating, 2016) Malaysia is the top ranking in Muslim tourist destinations with the increase total number of tourists coming. Islamic tourism is to enhance the relationship of fellow Muslims too and maintain friendliness in interaction, where the countries of Malaysia, UAE, and Turkey are taking seriously about this business to attract Muslim tourists according to (Henderson, 2017; MasterCard & CrescentRating, 2017). Malaysia is the largest Muslim total in 2010 of around 17 million people with 61.4% of Muslims. With the number of Muslims, business people take the opportunity to open halal products both halal food, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, logistics and many more which are subject to competition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hotel Industry in Malaysia

The hotel is a temporary place to stay to enjoy good service both from Food, Drinks, recreation areas and others (Medlik and Ingram, 2000). Based on a statement from (P. Jones and Lockwood 1989) the hotel is used for temporary sleep tourists but due to additional services such as restaurants that make the service better. This also affects the economy of the people because tourists will be shopping around area hotel where they are staying. According to (Yuhanis, 2007) in Malaysia, the hotel industry grew from 1994 which deals with tourist attractions which caused the two components to be very influential. In the Visit Malaysia event in 1990, there was a growing demand for rooms as well (Ching, 2018).

Guest satisfaction in Shariah-Compliant Hotel

Customer satisfaction in the hospitality and tourism industry will greatly depend on the front-line service providers since these employees are first to be in contact with the customer. Service is all about people and how they relate to one another and fulfil needs and expectations. The best possible service an organization can offer its customer is the personal touch. So it is essential for these employees to know the guest and their specific needs in order to serve them better. Being able to identify the guest as a Muslim and knowing their preferences goes a long way.

Guest satisfaction can be defined in various ways. According to Kotler et al. (1996), satisfaction is "the level of a person's felt state resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance (or outcome) in relation to the person's expectations." In brief, satisfaction level simply is a function of the difference between perceived performance and also expectation (Stahl, 1999).

Customer Loyalty

One important factor for a business hotel to survive and even grow is that there is a high level of loyalty from its customers. When it starts to be developed, a business will try to turn consumers into loyal customers, and after the business is running the next challenge is how to maintain customer loyalty. The effort is certainly not easy. It takes time, money, and a sound business strategy to make that happen. But when a business is really needed by customers, we just enjoy the results. Especially if the love of a brand truly enters the hearts and minds of customers, our business can be said to have entered the safe stage.

Facilities in Shariah-Compliant Hotel

Facilities at conventional hotels are very familiar with towels, hand towels. Face towel, soap, brushing teeth and slipper. However, with the concept of the *Shariah-Compliant Hotel* (SCH) facilities can be divided into two, namely public facilities and also room facilities (Imrie et al. 2002). Thus, the guest can feel comfortable with what the guest receives from SCH. facilities have a supporting factor to differentiate from conventional hotels and also Shariah-Compliant Hotels (SCH).

Building design In Shariah-Compliant Hotel

Building design in hotels is generally the most modern style in accordance with the times. In the *Shariah-Compliant Hotel* (SCH) the design of a hotel must be more to Islamic concepts such as art in the room. Usually in hotels also display paintings of people who are famous in the world, therefore the building design on SCH is a bit different. Not only that the building design is also focused on the bedroom and toilet position not facing the Qibla.

Food and Beverage in Shariah-Compliant Hotel

Malaysia is a country with the highest total Muslims, of course, restaurants in the Malaysian is halal, thus increasing the quality of services in restaurants as a precursor to the halal food law in the early 1980s (Riaz and Chaudry, 2004). In the restaurant, there is distribution and also production based on Shariah Islam to improve halal products (Nik Maheran et al., 2009). in general, in conventional hotels too many bars and selling alcohol in the restaurant, of course, the opposite of the *Shariah-Compliant Hotel* concept, where SCH hotels only provide halal food and drinks (Suzana & Che Wan Jasimah, 2006).

Grooming staff in Shariah-Compliant Hotel

Hotels in general, are very well known for Grooming Staff where the part to make the staff become disciplined. Staff becomes good looking especially in reception. Staff reception is the icon of a hotel Reception is like a flight attendant of a hotel. The staff serves all guests coming to the hotel so grooming staff is very important in hotel industry. Usually grooming staff is checked by the duty manager before the staff starts work. No less than the *Shariah-Compliant hotel* concept, it is different from Conventional hotels where Shariah hotels are not allowed to wear short clothes. *Shariah-Compliant Hotel* how to use it is that women must wear the hijab, long skirts are not tight. For men, they also have to be polite and almost the same as conventional hotels.

Shariah- Compliant Hotel in Malaysia

Islamic hospitality is embedded in Islamic religion, culture, and experience because Islam is a way of life. It is extensively practiced in the Middle East where Islam is originated. It offers traditional principles and custom for Muslim travelers (L. Kaaki, 2008). The concept of *Shariah-Compliant Hotel* (SCH) is because there is a request from guests in accordance with Shariah Islami to improve health for Muslims (C. J. Henderson 2017). However, there is lack of empirical research and article written on the concept of SCH that acknowledges the underdeveloped concept of SCH (P. Rosenberg 2009)

METHODS

To maximize Shariah-Compliant Hotel services in Malaysia, especially in Shah Alam, it must be tested with basic 5 Models Variable, which are a Restaurant (Food & Beverage), Grooming staff (Muslim Dress Code), Facilities, Building design, and Customer Loyalty. Total Population in Malaysia is 31.62 Million in 2019 (Source by Worldometers), through this study sample research is 208 respondents from various regions in Malaysia and provide public opinion of the Shariah-Compliant Hotel services. Result of reliability test of this research is a operating by SPSS 24.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Respondent demographic profile

Demographic Profile	Catagories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	139	66.8
	Female	69	33.2
	Total	208	100
Age	Under 20 years	16	7.7
	21-30 years	49	23.6
	31-40 years	106	51
	41-50 years	35	16.8
	51-60 years	2	1
	Total	208	100
Ethnicity/Race	Malay	164	78.8
	Chinese	21	10.1
	Indian	20	9.6
	Others	3	1.4
	Total	208	100
Nationality	Malaysian	199	95.7
	Non-Malaysian	9	4.3
	Total	208	100
Status	Single	79	38
	Married	123	59.1
	Others	6	2.9
	Total	208	100

Education	Secondary School	7	3.4
	Diploma	39	18.8
	Degree	141	67.8
	Master Degree	18	8.7
	PhD Degree	2	1
	Others	1	0.5
	Total	208	100
Job Title	Student	29	13.9
	Professional	106	51
	Businessman	72	34.6
	Others	1	0.5
	Total	208	100
Income (Monthly) Ringgit	2000 or less	27	13
	2001-4000	62	29.8
	4001-6000	95	45.7
	6001-8000	21	10.1
	8001-10000	3	1.4
	Total	208	100

Table above has described about details of the participants, eight data collected from respondents such as Gender, Age, Ethnicity/Race, Nationality, Status, Education, Job title and income. Total respondents is 208 from Shah Alam. In Gender segment male, 66.8% and Female 33.2%, majority duration, age from 31 to 40 years old with a total 51 %, Race majority is Malay 78.8% and Nationality is Malaysian with a total 95.7%, Status respondents majority is married, 59.1%, Majority respondents are Professional job title 51%, majority education level of the participants is Degree 67.8% and income from 4001-6000 is 45.7%. Moreover, Table was shown that participants are from Malaysia to Professional work that enjoy with the Shariah Hotel in Shah Alam.

Independent Variable

Table 2. Restaurant

	Waitress servants use hijab	Halal Certification Restaurant	Designated table for family, married couples and single customers	No alcohol/Bar services	The restaurant area is clean and organized	Variety of food is provided	The food served is still fresh
N Valid	208	208	208	208	208	208	208
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	4.12	4.51	4.00	4.36	4.57	4.43	4.43
Std. Deviation	.857	.774	.919	.927	.656	.698	.705

Very friendly workers	The price of each menu is as expected	Room service is very efficient in preparing the room for check-in	Breakfast is replaced with Pre-dawn meal during Ramadan	Breakfast served is very appetizing	Waiter are very neat and charismatic	Staff must be Muslim	The restaurant has an Islamic background music
208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4.36	4.25	4.30	4.30	4.25	4.18	3.71	3.64
.714	.788	.721	.734	.739	.825	.765	.702

Based on the first variable, which is "Food & Beverage (Restaurant)" can be seen from table 2. overall each question has an average value of 4 and above, there is two question whose value is below the average of four, its question number 14 "staff must be Muslim" thus this question has a peculiarity in the hearts of each respondent because they still accept Non -Muslim to become staff at Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH). Future research can focus on this question to be retested again with a total of more than 208 respondents to be surer that this question is a very important role in the Islamic hotel. In addition, there is also a question that strikes from the results of the above research, it has question number 15 " The Restaurant has Islamic background music " the average value is 3.64% this is the lowest value in this variable because logically it will indeed play Islamic songs in the restaurant. This question needs to be reviewed with a total respondent of more than 208. Besides that, it also focuses on the third question " designated table for family, married couples and single customers " This has a value of 4 with a total of 4.8% from the total 208 respondents disagreeing on this statement and therefore expect to increase seminars or give talk forums about Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH) and discuss the details of this section. However, overall all respondents has accepted for the first variable and the first hypothesis proven to be an important part of the Shariah-Compliant Hotel.

Table 3. Summary survey of Grooming staff (Muslim Dress Code) in Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH)

		The reception staffs are kind and friendly	The reception staffs are fluently speaking in English	The check-in procedure is very fast and does not require a long time	Staff reception clothes are very polite	Hotel service is very easy and not complicated in consulting guest problems	Manager on Duty is on standby in the lobby at all times
N	Valid	208	208	208	208	208	208
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.37	4.14	4.23	4.28	4.30	4.12
Std. Deviation		.690	.728	.732	.689	.695	.740

		Check out procedure is very easy	I always give tips for hotel employees	The number of staff at the hotel is enough to serve guests	Staff kitchen must be Muslim	Hair color must be natural (Male)	The concierge greets to every guest
		208	208	208	208	208	208
		0	0	0	0	0	0
		4.10	4.18	3.85	4.10	4.01	3.80
		.755	.781	.946	.764	.938	.772

Overall for this variable, it has reached the target based on the research objectives in chapter two. However, there is a tendency in question number eight and number eleven. The average total value is less than 4. For statement number eight is 'I always give tips for hotel employees' on average averaging 3.85. From the results, it can be seen that people are very lacking to give tips to workers. Tips there is a form of appreciation from guests to workers because they provide service for the satisfaction provided by the hotel. Usually, these tips will be obtained by reception staff and also the housekeeping department. Because they work interactions with guests directly. Daily staff gets tips from their guests who have a sense of being able to work in this field can motivate workers to be better staff. Besides that, question number eleven 'hair color must be natural' containing an average value of 3.8 has a unique feature for this purpose. That is, there needs to be a forum conference to discuss details about statement number eleven.

Table 4. Summary survey of facilities in Islamic hotel

Facilities In SCH		Access to the hotel is very easy	The hotel provided prayer room for staff and visitors	The toilet in the lobby area is clean	Easy to get parking when arriving at the hotel	Bellman staff is very helpful with my luggage	Security employees are helpful in finding for parking lots	Receptionist provides sufficient information about the hotel
N	Valid	208	208	208	208	208	208	208
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	4.21	4.47	4.45	4.35	4.28	4.27	4.29
	Std. Deviation	.805	.687	.693	.719	.749	.725	.733

Lots of parking space	Swimming pool are separately for male and female guests	Providing recreation areas for guests	Separate Gymnasium is provided for male and female guests	Prayer mats are provided by the hotel	Al Quran is provided by the hotel	Qibla signage is provided in every guest's room	Comfortable waiting room is provided for guests
208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4.25	4.15	4.26	4.25	4.40	4.43	4.44	4.37
.782	.854	.763	.875	.729	.771	.753	.776

Shariah-compliant hotels (SCH) are very much supported by facility provided by the hotel. Overall, it can be seen in Table 23 that the research objective in chapter one is answered because Facilities are very important in Islamic hotels. Based on the results of the research above, it can focus on statement number nine "Swimming pool are separately for male and female guests" This is the lowest value in this variable (Facilities). There is some suggest by respondent for this statement, which is adding a swimming pool for families, married couples and others. Because if a statement like that is how the husband and wife want to go to the pool to swim. Likewise also with those who have a family and bring their children. Through this research for independent variable number three "Facilities" answered there is indeed an influence for guest satisfaction with the facilities provided by the hotel. Besides that, with the data above, the Shariah Hotel still needs to be deepened for the sake of the government as a benchmark to formally establish Shariah-Compliant Hotels in Malaysia. Because until now the Islamic hotel has no legal requirement in this country.

Table 5. Summary survey of building design based on Islamic concept

Building Design in SCH		The lobby area of the hotel is clean	The lobby layout is attractive and practical	The price of the room meets my expectation	The design of the hotel is very good according to the theme	The bedroom position does not face the Qibla	The position of the toilet does not lead to the Qibla	The living room must have an Islamic nuance	Painting in the lobby has Islamic themes	Prayer time information is provided
N	Valid	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208	208
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	4.43	4.32	4.23	4.28	4.14	4.19	4.07	4.04	4.30
	Std. Deviation	.691	.714	.743	.715	.909	.873	.895	.897	.838

In the fourth Independent Variable is “*Building Design*” which emphasizes the design of a hotel with the concept of *Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH)*. Inside the Islamic concept hotel in Malaysia is very concerned about the details of the theme of the building both outside and inside the hotel. To satisfy the guest, it is indeed a difficult thing for business people, therefore through this research, we will explain and explore one by one what are the factors that influence this hypothesis four. We pay attention to the first statement ‘the lobby is the hotel is clean’ the average value is 4.43 so, according to the 208 respondent's view that in the area lobby it is clean and maintained and neat. There are still those who judge 'neutral' as many as 11.5%, meaning that the guest who filled out this survey still has little doubt about this statement. The challenge for business people to look for trade is 11.5%, which is valuing 'neutral'. The smallest value of this variable is question number eight 'Painting in the lobby has Islamic themes', meaning the concept of the theme in the lobby still needs to be developed such as the addition of Islamic knowledge books on the guest table for guests who are waiting for their rooms to be ready. Besides that, it is also possible for the hotel to provide paintings whose writings of hadith and Sunnah are written on the walls of the lobby.

Table 6. Summary customer loyalty

Customer Loyalty		Food provided by the restaurant by Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH) is very varied and is highly recommended for families	Employees at the Islamic hotel are good service to the guest who made me and my family come again	The facilities provided by Islamic hotels are very complete and suitable for visitors who are highly recommended for the Islamic religion	The Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH) building environment is comfortable and beautiful in accordance with Islamic art and will come again later.
N	Valid	208	208	208	208
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.22	4.17	4.27	4.22
Std. Deviation		.798	.785	.775	.798

Customer loyalty is a situation where the consumer has a positive attitude towards the brand, is committed to the brand and intends to continue buying in the future (Mowen and Minor, 2002: 89). Based on this research, it shows that customers have their own satisfaction which will increase their confidence in the loyalty that will come again to Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH). Because the Variable independent factors are very appropriate for the target factors customers feel when staying at the hotel. The key is if the customer feels satisfied with what he/her feels and will affect customer loyalty.

There is one important thing about customer loyalty above, which is the aspect of positive preparedness in the form of feeling happy. Repeated purchases of the same product may occur due to force, not accompanied by feelings of pleasure. For example, a user does not have an alternative product to meet their needs because in a place that can or is comfortably reached only one product is available. Forced purchases are difficult to apply once again in the future if the conditions that force them do not exist. For example, if there are a number of alternative products that can fulfill the customer's location in the future, then it is difficult to expect so that he will continue to buy and consume the product beforehand.

Whereas according to Oliver, customer loyalty is a commitment held in depth to buy or support products or services that are of interest in the future even though the influence of the situation and marketing efforts have the potential to cause customers to switch. On that basis, it can be said that the following definitions strongly emphasize the position of commitment to always be the main thing. If he is someone who is fully committed, he ignores the number of competitors and alternative products or services owned by competitors. That person will always be loyal and take place in the long term (Kotler and Keller, 2009: 138).

Table 7. Summary of result independent variable

No	Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Restaurant (Food & Beverage)	4.23	0.808
2	Grooming staff (Muslim Dress Code)	4.13	0.781
3	Facilities	4.32	0.761
4	Building design	4.22	0.808
5	Customer Loyalty	4.22	0.789

Based on the table 6, variables are accepted by the customer that proof above result > 4 from 5 Scales. The highest of variable is Facilities (4.32 from 5) due of customer was need Muslim facilities provided in the hotel, following by Restaurant variable (4.23) that guest has satisfied about Food & Beverage provided by the SCH. Moreover, it is the similar result between Customer Loyalty and Building Design (4.22) and the last but not least is Grooming staff (Servicer Muslim Dress Code) (4.13) is the lowest result and need to improve this particular part on Shariah Compliant Hotel.

Through this research, it will develop a new innovation for hospitality knowledge that makes the place of a brainstorm between businessmen. Because a satisfaction with customers is the main goal that makes the basic material certainly affects customer loyalty. Here describe the supporting indicators that are the basic ingredients in achieving the research objectives. Besides that, there have also been some changes from the start of the research to the stage of managing data such as the addition of frameworks. " Grooming Staff " to 'grooming staff (Muslim dress code)' because of this to make easy the reader understands about the variables in the questionnaire. When the proposal defence also has a number of recommendations from the panel, that is, changing the dependent variable to mediating because the dependent variable can be written: "customer loyalty" (indirectly there are additional variables in the conceptual framework in chapter three. This research can identify the characteristics of an Islamic hotel.

DISCUSSION

Shariah-Compliant hotel (SCH) is a new field in the hotel industry both in Asia and in the world. The hotel itself is a high-class business that is generally only for sleeping or temporary resting places. As the development of the era increasingly deepened and developed in the science of hotels. In chapter five this explains in detail every variable that influences the importance of growing the Islamic hotel. Here there are four variables that support customer satisfaction, where customer satisfaction is closely related to customer loyalty. Faithful customers that mean you have a high chance to get repeat business, and also free marketing from them through word of mouth. But, to foster and maintain loyalty it requires some correct tricks and tips. Take the story from guest and always communicate with customers. Don't make them feel they are just a place for you to profit but make them feel they can afford a problem solving on your part. Give them value and you will get more value from them. Faithful customers will give multiple returns. For business triumphs, think of long periods of time and how to foster customer loyalty and not just to get an official sale. We are aware that the quality of products and services will determine the success of a business. Low quality products and services will certainly get problems if customers feel they are deceived by buying them. Not as much as it is, a business news about selling low-quality products will also be easily spread by customers who are not complacent.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In the above section, conclusions were reached on why *Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH)* in Shah-Alam. Therefore it is worth to discuss the implication and recommendation for these significant variables in order for the entrepreneur to overcome business failure. The implication and recommendations for this purpose are discussed mainly under Islamic hotel. Here will be explained based on the implications of the results research. Through this research, the

government can become a benchmark for making rules for hotels with a concept “*Shariah-Compliant Hotel*”. Because this is very important for businessman in fulfilling the requirements in an Islamic hotel such as Halal Food has implemented in Malaysia. Then from that department “*Jabatan Kemajuan Islam Malaysia (Jakim)*” must be able to deepen in developing a hotel business in Malaysia. Moreover, in industry for the hotel can read as knowledge and advance anything that causes the hotel rating to decline. Especially for hotels that have implemented Islamic hotels. In the future, the company can also read the results of this research through the characteristics of *Shariah-Compliant hotel (SCH)*. Therefore, there is no one in Malaysia who has applied in the subject matter of *Islamic Hotels / Shariah-Compliant Hotel*. So, expect the government or the university to raise this material. To facilitate and explain that *Shariah-Compliant Hotel (SCH)* is a new innovation that becomes an attraction for the future.

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